

POSSIBILITIES OF REFORMING THE LOGICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the solution of the problem of training teachers to develop general logical skills in mathematics in primary school students. Based on the constructed system of groups of general logical skills, the author finds his own approach to solving the problem, which became the basis of the author's model of logical and methodological training of university students majoring in "Pedagogy and Methodology of Primary Education" in the process of studying the course "Methodology of Teaching Mathematics".

Keywords: model of training teachers, methods of teaching mathematics, professional and pedagogical competence, logical and methodological skills

INTRODUCTION

The goal of modern education is the general cultural, personal and cognitive development of students, ensuring such a key competence as the ability to learn. In this case, knowledge, skills and abilities are considered as derivatives of the corresponding types of targeted actions, i.e. they are formed, applied and maintained in close connection with the active actions of the students themselves. The quality of knowledge acquisition is determined by the diversity and nature of the types of universal actions [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An analysis of psychological, pedagogical and educational-methodical literature has shown that the teacher training system does not pay due attention to such skills, although there are certain achievements in this area. Beginning in the XX century, the work of N. F. Talyzina, P. A. Shevarev, and P. Ya. Galperin raised the issue of the importance of general logical skills as a type of general skills in teaching any subject. N. F. Talyzina proves that when organizing the process of acquiring knowledge, much attention should be paid to the actions that students use as a means of acquiring this knowledge. If the learning objectives involve the use of knowledge in actions that students do not possess, then learning should simultaneously ensure the acquisition of these actions and knowledge.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thus, the contradiction between the requirements of modern society for the training of primary education teachers (in the area of developing general logical skills in mathematics in primary school students in the educational process of a pedagogical university) and the insufficient development of the scientific and methodological foundations of this process in practice is becoming increasingly obvious. Overcoming this contradiction determines the research problem: how to ensure the training of primary education teachers to develop general logical skills in mathematics in primary school students in the process of their professional training. To solve this problem, it is necessary to theoretically substantiate, design and implement in practice a model for training teachers to develop general logical skills in mathematics in primary school students and to identify the pedagogical conditions for its effective functioning [2].

In order to implement the model of training primary education teachers to develop general logical skills in primary school students, developed in the theoretical part of the study, three stages of the experiment were identified in the logic of the competence approach: ascertaining, formative, and control and evaluation. The experiment was attended by full-time students - two groups of 18 people (experimental groups) and correspondence students - two groups of 18 people (experimental and control groups); an experimental group of working teachers who are students of the correspondence department - 18 people. Thus, a total of 90 people took part in the experiment. The experiment was conducted within the framework of the developed model, in the amount of academic hours allocated according to the compiled program of the course "Methodology of Teaching Mathematics" and during the passage of pedagogical practices by students. To identify the level of preparation of students (future primary education teachers) to develop general logical skills in mathematics, the criteria were used as generalized indicators.

The 1st criterion shows the level of methodological skills and includes the following indicators [3]:

- identification of a group of general logical skills, which is the focus of each mathematical task;
- determination of the type of error made by the student (or possible error), its methodological description; possible difficulties in completing tasks by the student;
- description of methodological work to prevent errors.

The 2nd criterion shows the level of cognitive activity: representation; reproduction; skills and abilities; creativity.

At the formative stage of the experiment, the process of testing the model was carried out, the process of training teachers took place on the basis of the principles of goal-setting, integration, functional completeness, systematicity, personal orientation. An important component of the model is the content of the course "Methodology of Teaching Mathematics", each section of which ends with research assignments for students, developed on the basis of groups of general logical skills. In general, at the formative stage of work with students, both traditional technologies and problem-oriented and project-organized ones were used. Periodically monitoring the formation of competencies of independent cognitive activity of students as a characteristic of professional growth, it was necessary to make adjustments to the content of the course, to the developed teaching methods, and also to search for new forms, teaching methods, and methodological techniques.

CONCLUSION

Considering that the conducted research is a part of a long process of training primary education teachers to develop general logical skills in primary school students, and considering the positive results of the research, the proposed model can be considered effective. The completed research allows us to conclude that the goal set at the beginning of the work has been achieved

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